

A Reflective Critique Report

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Introduction

As a Master of Management (MM) student myself, one of the Core Modules we are required to take is the Organisational Behaviour (OB) module which is the requirement set by the faculty School of Business and Economics of our university. Before taking the module, I was genuinely interested with the module as the word 'behaviour' itself reflects the connection to human behaviour and social psychology (iEduNote, n.d.) which is a subject that I am particularly interested in. I am the type of person who would read endlessly about the different personalities especially when it comes to Myers Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) personality type and would always try to type others based on their MBTI personalities (www.16personalities.com). When I noticed that OB is inclusive of this particular topic, apart from other behavioural concepts, I was enthusiastic to learn this module and how the new knowledge offered in this module would help me understand its application to the future organisational settings.

At the beginning of the semester during the OB module introduction, we were introduced to the assignments we were expected to complete. We were given two projects; individual research and the other one was a group case study research consisting of three or four students. Henceforth, this reflective critique report will signify the experience and challenges that I faced along the way in regard to both individual and group settings, and the certain things I would have done differently throughout the semester of taking the OB module.

My experience and challenges

Individual setting and how it was addressed

It is important to note that I am a graduate student who majored in Mathematics for my previous bachelor's degree. Those who took Mathematics would understand how much we do not practice writing academic papers as we deal mostly with equations and numbers. With little to no experience and knowledge of writing and conducting research, I was usually clueless about how to begin and uncertain with my work. This is one of the major challenges I faced and still struggles to cope as a Master in Management student where students' assignments depend heavily on writing essays and reports, aside from the few presentations and uncountable group discussions. I was somewhat unaware of how much writing was needed for this MM course, even though I was fully informed by the seniors prior to taking the course. With the addition to the concurrent COVID-19 pandemic, lectures were limited to online video conferences, physical one-hour tutorial classes and the exclusion of examination percentages which added significantly more workload than it normally would prior to the pandemic. Hence, without much expectation I set on myself, it dawned on me that I needed to learn the proper way to write essays and academic papers.

Admittedly, my first essay assignment (not an OB module) was terrible. A question was posed by my lecturer about a topic for an essay assignment and I just simply answered the question in paragraphs of at least 4000 words without any abstract or headings for the paragraphs. With added sparing literature here and there, I did not know much about how to properly cite the references and where to look for academic literature reviews. However, throughout the semester as I write more essays and reports, I have productively learned and improved as writing requires me to read numerous journal articles and research papers, with addition to learning from friends and Youtube videos. This enables me to compare my own work, understand the basic structure and the key aspects of academic papers. I also learned the use of APA referencing style which is the only style that my university accepts. This was not possible without the help of a new friend from the same MM course who willingly gave a

complete guide for referencing and whom I met physically for the first time. Not to mention, the lecturer to the first essay assignment had given constructive feedback and this had facilitated me to progress significantly. This prior experience has slowly boosted my confidence and motivation in writing essay assignments as I gradually acquire knowledge and skills. This can be linked to the theory of Bandura (1986) where

“Self-confidence poses as a common cognitive mechanism for mediating people's motivation, thought patterns, emotional reactions, and behaviour.”
(pp. 178)

(as cited by National Research Council [NRC], 1994)

Bandura (1986), as cited by NRC (1994), also highlighted that confidence can be seen through the belief of one's performance accomplishments, depending on whether the person self-monitors themselves positively or negatively (pp. 178). In my case, I view the experience I underwent as an accomplishment and a success and thus, it has positively affected my self-confidence, behaviour as well as my emotional reactions. Furthermore, according to the research by Locke et al. (1984), as cited by NRC (1994), when a person's belief on their self-confidence is strong (as evaluated independently from their goal), they tend to set higher goals for themselves and that they are firmer to their commitments. I strongly agree with this statement because as I progress, I noticed I became more committed to the MM course I am taking and wanted to achieve more without myself realising.

When it comes to the individual work for this OB module, I was really struggling to understand what was expected from the lecturer and I believed my lack of knowledge and experience at the time was majorly contributing to my hesitancy. At the beginning of the semester, a step-by-step timeline or a schedule was given by the lecturer to complete the two individual and group projects throughout the semester. We are aware that we should follow the timeline, however, I personally did not expect that they were actually a schedule of deadlines for the steps for the entire semester. When I first found out from a group mate, it was only a few days to the very first submission date (which was a research proposal for the individual research). Although I have started with some research and readings after the task was given, it placed me in a situation of panic and unpreparedness. I managed to submit the research proposal on time but by then, I realised there were more deadlines to catch up, following the schedule. By the end of the semester, I felt drained and lost my motivation as we spent most of our time where almost every week we had multiple deadlines to catch up to along with other modules as well.

As cited by Capa, Audiffren and Ragot (2008), Brehm and Self (1989) had articulated a motivation theory where “effort is expected to be proportional to the task's difficulty up to the point that participants are no longer willing to invest the energy required to succeed.” The upper limit or the optimal motivation is called potential motivation where one's motivation can range within high and low. Eubanks, Wright and Williams (2002) have noted the relationship between potential motivation and the difficulty of a task (as cited by Capa et al., 2008). For the very easy tasks, it should be seen that it is possible to succeed and are worthwhile for someone with low or high potential motivation. With difficult tasks, energy or effort is proportional to its difficulty and success is seen as possible to be achieved, but the task becomes worthwhile only when the person's potential motivation is high. However, when a task is considered very difficult, the invested effort becomes low and success is seen as impossible despite the person having a high potential motivation.

I would personally list myself as having a high potential motivation or at least above average. As mentioned earlier, the level for very difficult tasks is exactly relatable to the situation I underwent when it comes to the MM course. Not only the tasks are considered difficult, it was overwhelmingly too much to handle. I fully understand that some of my peers who took this MM course have dropped out when they said they are already pressured with the tasks given from the beginning of the semester, there was so much work even from the start! Although I did manage to cope with my first semester, it has affected my motivation gradually and at this point, the grades I will achieve no longer matter for me as long as I pass all of my modules.

Group setting and how it was addressed

When we were introduced to the group case study research, we were asked to conduct primary research of a topic that we have chosen from a given list. At the time, my group of three did not realise that there was a new announcement from the lecturer regarding the topic list. We ended up with three to four case study topics to choose from because the other 22 topics were already taken by the other groups. So we did not have much choice in choosing the topic we were interested in and decided to take the one that we believed to be the most doable amongst the four that were not yet taken. The topic was about “the motivation of *gerai* or stall halal entrepreneurship” which we believed that finding or conducting the sample was easy. It actually was easy since stalls can be found anywhere in Brunei and the majority of the country’s population are Muslims, which we initially define the Muslim entrepreneurs as halal entrepreneurs.

In the group, I was the only one among us three who knew nothing much about conducting research. I actually felt a little left out since I was not able to contribute as much as I would like to. I did inform them that I had not had much experience with research, let alone primary research. I felt bad still, even though they kept reassuring me that it was okay. I also made sure that I contribute as much as possible even to the things that seem trivial such as creating a Whatsapp group or creating a folder on Google Drive. I was glad that my two group mates were very supportive and helped me explain the things I did not understand in conducting research. With my underdeveloped skills, I would say, has made the group case study topic difficult for me to grasp and collect the relevant data. The topic itself was pretty difficult for us to understand as we progressed to researching the literature reviews.

We have found that the characteristics of halal entrepreneurs generally relates to the individual’s or entrepreneurs’ Islamic values such as their relationship towards Allah and their belief or fear of the Hereafter. Therefore, finding the sample was a challenge as the halal entrepreneurs’ characteristics were difficult to evaluate and are considered as immeasurable in which this also has created a gap or limitation to the research and the data collected. After multiple discussions, we manage to agree to somewhat ‘reduce the rigidity’ of the characteristics of halal entrepreneurs. We decided that when asking the interview questions (qualitative data collection was used to conduct the research), we can just simply pinpoint the certain keywords or ask certain questions that may indirectly lead to their religious values. For example, when asking about their daily routine prior to carrying their business early in the morning at their stall, we could find out whether or not they mentioned about performing their prayers before dawn. This could reflect how much they are prioritising their relationship towards Allah and thus, they are considered as halal entrepreneurs. Moving forward, we managed to finish collecting the data and proceed to data analysis and writing the report.

As we progress through our assignments and starting to find a good rhythm with the deadlines, the faculty have decided not to approve anymore Ethics Form. Ethics Form is a form which requires us to state our research questions, the aim of the study, the interview or survey questions and how we are going to consider the ethics of conducting the data collection for primary research. After being approved by the faculty, only then we can proceed with our research. Since both of our individual and group projects depend on primary data collection, we had no choice but to change our research method to secondary data collection. Hence, most of the students who are in the OB module became frustrated and demotivated after the weeks we have spent to prepare the research. Gladly, our group had submitted the form early and managed to get the approval. For my individual work, however, I myself responded as both positively and negatively. I thought that I would not have to submit what might turn to be a low-quality primary research report. On the other hand, I would say I was disappointed because I have spent many hours on one module which has made me unable to pay equal attention to other modules. I understand that these are the things that are out of my control but I could have done things differently with the things that are actually under my control.

What might I have done differently

There are a few things that had happened along the way this semester, though they are not all mentioned in this paper, they are not always within my control. In this section, I will highlight the things that I have learned and how I might have done some things differently.

For the most part, I have been lacking the skills needed in conducting any sort of research and writing academic research papers. Although I have learned along the way, I realised that I could have improved even further. I was aware I was lacking the knowledge, but what I did not do was that setting the goal for myself to achieve. According to Edwin Locke in the 1960s, he noted that the major source of work motivation is when a person targets to achieve a certain goal (as cited by Thompson and Lumen Learning). Therefore, I believe that if I have set a goal where I want to achieve a certain level of proficiency, I would be more motivated and determined. This may help me to be more proactive in learning how to conduct research and compose quality academic papers. Even though this is a skill that can be developed with effort, determination and knowledge, I am also aware that any skills that we wish to learn will take an extended amount of time.

Most of the modules I took have initially set out a schedule of the assignment deadlines, tests and presentation. Despite all that, I was unable to properly manage my time, not only for self-study time but also for a group work or discussion. I have allocated a certain time for me to do the assignments, but sometimes I did not follow them strictly especially when I felt tired or demotivated with the many assignments. However, in spite of being demotivated I should still follow the schedule I set for myself with the end in mind as the main motivation and I should remember back the reason why I take MM course in the first place. This would also help if I remind myself my intrinsic motivation where according to Deci and Ryan (2000), it “represents the most self-determined or autonomous behaviour regulation by inherent interest, enjoyment and satisfaction” (as cited by Sportlyzer Academy, n.d.). In other words, my intrinsic motivation would be the enjoyment I felt when writing, reading and acquiring knowledge in general (Santos-Longhurst, 2019). Thus, remembering my intrinsic motivation should be internally rewarding when doing the certain activities and be motivated.

Conclusion

In conclusion, throughout the semester (first semester of the MM course) I have learned so much new knowledge and also gained and improved some skills. I also learned that I should set a measurable goal for myself in order to improve exponentially. I also learned that I should set the schedule for myself and take the advantage where lecturers have already set the assignment deadlines from the very beginning of the semester. I should be able to divide my time for doing assignments of both the individual ones and the group as well. Since these are the things I can control, I should also be ready and not be driven by emotion when something unexpected happens and that I should always see things positively and be grateful for the other things I have acquired.

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